

The strategy of sustainable agriculture development in the border region of West Kalimantan support food security

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ABSTRACT

Intensive agricultural development has an ecological impact by decreasing the productivity of land and plants. The natural resource potential of both food and livestock crops in the border region of West Kalimantan has the potential to be a producer of sustainable agriculture. Food products in this area partially implement sustainable agriculture. Sustainable agricultural development strategies include; provide understanding, counseling, demonstration plots to the community. Steps to strengthen food security include; increased food production capacity, revitalization and restructuring of food institutions, food independent village development. The strategy pursued through local germplasm exploration, technology availability, extension systems.

Keywords: sustainable agriculture, availability of technology and extension systems

INTRODUCTION

The green revolution of the 1960s and 1970s that resulted in dramatic increases in yields in developing countries in Asia, now shows a decrease in productivity. Intensive agriculture carried out without adherence to scientific principles and ecological aspects has led to loss of soil health, and depletion of freshwater and agrobiodiversity resources. With the transfer of progressive arable land for non-agricultural purposes, the challenge of feeding the population continues to grow. Agricultural businesses will use a lot of forest land. Furthermore, with food availability through production, there are millions of marginal agriculture, fishermen and rural families who have no land have very little or no access due to lack of income-generating livelihoods (Kesavan and Swaminathan, 2007).

Agricultural development in the West Kalimantan border area is directed towards sustainable agricultural development as a material for the implementation of sustainable development. Sustainable agricultural development (including rural development) is an important strategic issue that is of concern and discussion in all countries today. Sustainable agricultural

development, besides being a destination, has also become a paradigm of agricultural development patterns.

The border areas of the country have a strategic influence in determining the boundaries of state sovereignty, encouraging the achievement of the welfare of surrounding communities through the utilization of natural resources, and affecting the defense and security of the state. The Ministry of National Development Planning through the “National Medium-Term Development Plan 2015-2019” targets the direction of the Kalimantan border development policy to realize the gateway for economic and trade relations between countries. General strategies that can be applied in the direction of the policy include: 1) increasing economic access in border areas (Entikong, Aruk-Paloh, Badau, Nunukan and others), 2) enhancing interregional relations by improving and developing road facilities in villages and sub-districts; 3) enhancement of energy and communications facilities; 4) improvement of accessibility of education and health facilities; 5) development of international trade by utilizing local resource potential; and 6) enhancing defense and security to maintain state sovereignty (Imelda, 2018)

The development of Indonesia’s border areas includes the development of basic facilities and infrastructure, development of tourism, plantation and forestry development, agricultural development and human resource development. Raswita and Utama (2013), state that efforts to improve the welfare of communities in a region begin by encouraging the increase and growth of economic activity in the region. The high physical, social and cultural diversity of the border community requires an accurate, balanced and well-planned development approach (Priyanto and Diwyanto, 2014). In addition, efforts to develop border areas should also be supported by strengthening the capacity of local government institutions (Marwasta, 2016).

The economic activities of border communities are generally traditional, especially in agricultural and trade activities (Marihandono, 2011). Communities are constrained by low levels of education, lack of skills and uncertainty in jobs and incomes. This leads to a decrease in income and welfare of border communities. Frontier areas have the opportunity to develop as they are supported by the availability of potential natural resources and sufficient labor. Efforts to promote the development of border areas require programs that can facilitate communities in accessing potential resources and to improve the welfare of communities in the border areas. In the early stages of regional development, the agricultural sector is the main focus of economic activity, because it can create jobs, increase income and welfare community. The development of the agricultural

sector is also an appropriate option in an effort to increase household and regional food security (Syarief, et al., 2014). Todaro and Smith (2003) stated that the development of agriculture in rural areas plays an important role to support the the economy.

Central issues related to agricultural problems in border areas include: 1) the socio-economic disparities between communities living on the borders of Indonesia and neighboring countries, 2) food distribution constraints at household level due to limited transportation facilities, limited storage time, and high transportation cost; 3) conversion of agricultural land in border area into residential land, trade, industry, and other physical infrastructure activities, so farming area is a kind of marginal land that often less appropriate or unsuitable for agricultural activities, and 4) the inability of the poor people to provide enough food so that many people still ignore the aspects of balanced nutrition and food security (Susilo, 2013). The objective of this review is to develop strategies for the sustainability agricultural in the border area of West Kalimantan to support food security.

LEISA (Low External Input and Sustainable Agriculture) System Development

Most farmers are limited in access to artificial inputs from outside the LEISA system as a viable option for farmers. Technology is needed that normally utilizes local resources efficiently. Farmers who are now implementing high external input farming (HEIA) can reduce pollution and costs and increase the efficiency of external inputs by applying several LEISA techniques. The application of agroecological knowledge to farmers and scientists so that external inputs and inputs can be combined in such a way as to convert and strengthen natural resources, increase productivity and guarantees and avoid impacts on the environment (Reijtjes, et al., 1999).

LEISA refers to the following forms of agriculture ((Reijtjes, et al., 1999).

- a. Trying to optimize the utilization of existing local resources by combining various components of the farming system, namely plants, animals, soil, water, climate and humans so that they complement each other and provide the greatest synergy effect.
- b. Trying to find ways to use external inputs only when needed to complement elements that are lacking in the ecosystem and improve biological, physical and human resources. In utilizing external inputs, primary attention is given to the maximization of recycling and minimizing environmental damage.

Table 2. Base Potential in the Agriculture and Plantation Sector

No	District	Sub District	Agriculture	Plantation
1.	Sambas	Sajingan Besar Paloh	Rice	Rubber and Cacao Coffee and Pepper
2.	Bengkayang	Jagio Babang Siding	Crops Crops and vegetable	Coconut Rubber and Cacao
3.	Sanggau	Sekayam Entikong	- Crops and vegetable	- Rubber
4.	Sintang	Ketungau Hulu Ketungau Tengah	Rice Crops	Rubber Rubber
5.	Kapuas Hulu	Kedamin Puring Kencana Badau Batang Lupar Embaloh Hulu Putussibau Empanang	Rice Rice Crops Rice and fruits Rice Rice dan fruits Rice	Rubber and Cacao - - Rubber Rubber and Cacao Rubber Rubber

Source: Mayono, et al., 2001

From the aspect of food security, the West Kalimantan border area is not permanent food insecure area. This condition is reflected in the availability of food with a harvested area approach in each sub-district directly adjacent (Table 3).

Livestock commodities that dominate are cattle and pigs (Table 4). Farming of cattle and pigs is mostly semi-intensive. Livestock during the day are released, at night they are grounded. Mostly there has been no integration of crops and livestock. Integration of plants and livestock is in Bengkayang Regency namely the integration of goats and peppers, integration of cattle and corn, Integration of goats and pepper is quite successful in Seluas District. Pepper plants use gliricidae as a climbing pole. Gliricidae is used as goat feed. Goat manure is used as pepper fertilizer. Whereas the integration of cattle and corn is applied to farmers in Sanggau Ledo and Seventeen Districts. Corn leaves at the age of 50 days can be used as animal feed. Cow dung is used as corn fertilizer

PROCEEDING OF INTERNATIONAL WORKSHOP AND SEMINAR

Innovation of Environmental-Friendly Agricultural Technology Supporting Sustainable Food Self-Sufficiency
ISBN 978-602-344-252-2

Table 3. Harvest area of food crops, vegetables and plantations in the border area of West Kalimantan Province

District	Sub-district	Comodity						
		Rice	Corn	Vegetable	Palm Oil	Rubber	Cacao	Pipper
Sambas	Paloh	8.002			2.636	1.939		460
	Sajingan Besar	1.964			1.687	5.936		135
Bengkayang	Jagoi Babang	1.205	174		27.252	1.998	58	112
	Siding	736	61			7.248	208	216
Sanggau	Entikong	543		118	1.738	3.128	1.533	1080
	Sekayam	3.311		213	25.180	3.311	853	881
Sintang	Ketungau Hulu	1.153	36		25545	4.114	65	464
	Ketungau Tengah	1.292	92		3784	4.665		271
Kapuas Hulu	Puring Kencana	384			6174	683		
	Badau	333			11.207	986		
	Batang Lupar	1.004			2.135	1.294		
	Embaloh Hulu	761				2.500		
	Putusibau Selatan	2.827				1.827		
	Empanang	990				1.130		

Source: Sub District in Number, 2016, 2017

Table 4. Livestok commodity potensial in the Border area West Kalimantan Province

District	Sub District	Type of livestock			
		Cow	Goat	Pork	
Sambas	Paloh		1.008	1.249	385
	Sajingan Besar		65	39	2.271
Bengkayang	Jagoi Babang		580	420	1.417
	Siding		41	39	36
Sanggau	Entikong				
	Sekayam		447	547	4.930
Sintang	Ketungau Hulu		35	40	2.722
	Ketungau Tengah		469	477	4.789
Kapuas Hulu	Puring Kencana		4		480
	Badau		17		1.401
	Batang Lupar		11	27	2.573
	Embaloh Hulu		153	6	1.668
	Putusibau Selatan		1.356	245	2.282
	Empanang				1.726

Source: Sub District in Number, 2016, 2017

Agricultural Cultivation Practices in West Kalimantan Border Areas

Agricultural cultivation, especially rice plants in the West Kalimantan Border region have not fully implemented sustainable agricultural cultivation. In general, farmers in this area use pesticides in preparation for land cultivation. Farmers in the border area are mostly Dayaks. The farming culture of shifting cultivation still exists. With limited land, farming culture is abandoned. The present condition of rice cultivation is land that is relatively high. Labor limitations and expensive labor wages are the limiting factors. The rice planting system still uses human labor with a tugal system. Planting machines from government assistance have not met the needs of farmers. Tile planting technology with a spacing of 20 x 20 cm, mostly local varieties with a potential below 2 tons per hectare. Fertilization is still using chemical fertilizers. Most farmers in controlling pests and diseases still use chemical pesticides.

Plantation cultivation is still conventional. The clearing of plantation land in Sumatra and Kalimantan still uses burning methods that cause smoke which disrupts health and even flight activities, both in the burning area and in neighboring countries (Singapore and Malaysia). The pattern of rice production has also not been able to anticipate and adapt the impacts of climate change so that in certain areas of production centers experiencing crop failure due to drought or flooding. Government efforts to produce drought-resistant rice varieties or withstand waterlogging with certain cropping patterns already exist, but the Petany community still does not fully understand and practice it (Directorate of Food and Agriculture, 2014)

Conventional agricultural development practices have a serious impact. Untung (2008) reports that the effects of conventional agricultural development practices include; (a) increase in surface erosion, floods and landslides, (b) decrease in soil fertility, (c) loss of soil organic matter, (d) soil salinity and irrigation and soil sedimentation, (e) increase in water and sewage pollution due to chemical fertilizers, domestic waste pesticides, (f) eutriikfasi water bodies, (g) pesticide residues and other hazardous materials in the environment and food that threaten public health and market rejection, (h) degradation of agricultural biodiversity, loss of local wisdom, (i) contribution in the process of global warming, (j) increase in unemployment, (k) decrease in employment, increase in social gap and number of smallholders in rural areas, (l) increase in poverty and malnutrition in rural areas, (m) dependence of farmers on government and agrochemical industry companies .

The Strategy for Sustainable Agricultural Development in Border Areas Supports Food Security

Sustainable agriculture development in the West Kalimantan border area is quite potential. Sustainable agricultural products from Raja Uncak's rice from Kapuas Hulu, beliah rice from Bengkayang, brown rice from Sanggau District has been traded to Malaysia. To safeguard these products, strategies for sustainable agricultural development are needed, among others;

1. Providing understanding and counseling to the community, especially the younger generation, about the importance of the concept of sustainable agriculture.
2. Making sustainable agriculture demonstration plots in each District BPP for the implementation of sustainable agriculture,
3. Establish cooperation with Agricultural Vocational Schools in socializing and implementing sustainable agriculture as well as for internships for vocational students.
4. Patterns of rice production and other food crops must be developed so that they are environmentally friendly and able to anticipate and adapt themselves to climate change. Environmentally friendly production patterns can be built through the application of organic production (including the use of organic fertilizers and pesticides), specific high-value location seeds, and water saving. While anticipation and adaptation to climate change can be done by adjusting the planting schedule based on weather forecasts and the use of superior rice varieties that are resistant to drought or withstand waterlogging for a long time (Directorate of Food and Agriculture, 2014).
5. Priority strategies that can be applied to the development of a sustainable agricultural sector in the border region of West Kalimantan are empowering farmers in the application of harvesting and post-harvest technology innovations. Through the introduction of technology, farmers can produce products that have added value so that they can be exported. Long-term goals can improve the quality and welfare of border communities (Imelda, 2018).
6. Hold an exhibition, field meeting, field school with the theme "sustainable agriculture" in each border district,

Strategic steps to strengthen food independence in the border area include (Burhansyah, 2013).

1. Increasing Sustainable Border Food Production Capacity

The importance of increasing production capacity considering the border area is a 4T-characterized area (remote, scattered, isolated and left behind) so that food availability is difficult. It is hoped that an increase in production capacity can increase food independence. The aim of increasing

production is to minimize food dependence from neighboring countries, and can meet domestic needs.

2. Revitalization and Restructuring of Existing Food Institutions: Village Granary

The condition of food institutions in border areas is largely unable to play a role in helping the welfare of farmers. The existence of the village granary as a food institution has not been optimized. Revitalization and Restructuring of food institutions in the border areas is endeavored to provide the right and profitable container for farmers.

3. Development of Food Independent Villages

The Food Independent Village Program that has been implemented by the district government needs to be sustainable. Activities include; establishment of food independent village working groups, formation of village food teams, establishment of affinity groups, formation of village financial institutions, assistance, technical training, mentoring and monitoring.

From the existing local potential conditions, the availability of technology, extension systems, market opportunities, the strategies adopted to build food independence in the border area of Sambas regency are necessary steps, among others;

1. Exploration of Local Food Nutrition Plasma; Exploring Local Food Nutrition Plasma in the Border Area, inventory and conservation (collection) of local rice germplasm in the kabasen border area of Sambas, West Kalimantan.
2. Technology availability; Conduct site-specific technology studies on local food commodities with environmentally friendly technology, cheap, available on site. This is because the condition of the border area is far from the center of the sale of production facilities so that production facilities (seeds, fertilizers and medicines) are needed at the location.
3. Extension System; The condition of lack of extension workers in the border area, it is necessary to develop extension workers from the community. Self-help extension agents can come from youth, community leaders, traditional leaders, religious leaders. Self-help extension agents are trained from the regency, province and BPTP West Kalimantan. Each instructor is given sufficient equipment, among others; motorized vehicle, laptop, modem, in focus, camera. In addition, self-help extension agents are given money to conduct demonstration plots of new technology to increase food productivity. It is also necessary to build a place to carry out counseling activities, in the form of agribusiness saung or clinic.

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CONCLUSIONS

The potential of food crops commodities in the border region of West Kalimantan include rice and secondary crops. Commodity of rubber and oil palm plantations. The dominant animals include cattle and pigs.

Agricultural cultivation of food crops, vegetables and plantations still uses conventional methods. The principle of sustainable agriculture has not been fully implemented by border farmers. The strategy of sustainable agriculture development in the border region of West Kalimantan, namely providing understanding, counseling, demonstration plots, exhibitions, field meetings on the importance of sustainable agriculture.

Steps to strengthen food security in the border area include; Continuous Improvement of Border Regional Food Production Capacity, Revitalization and Restructuring of Existing Food Institutions: Village Barns, Food Independent Village Development. The strategies adopted include; Local Food Germplasm Exploration, Technology Availability and Extension System

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